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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF TREATMENT OF MANDIBULAR
FRACTURES IN THREE DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES BY
OSTEOSYNTHESIS AND TO KNOW POSTOPERATIVE
COMPLICATIONS****¹Dr. Hafiz Hasan Fazal Sheikh, ²Dr. Aisha Zahoor, ³Dr. Zoya Manzoor**¹ Medical Officer, DHQ Hospital Hafizabad² Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi³ House Officer, DHQ Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan**Abstract:**

Purpose: The aim of this analysis was to know different postoperative complications linked with various methods used for the mandibular fractures treatment.

Study Design: An interventional Quasi-Experimental Study.

Place and Duration: In the Oral and Maxillofacial Department of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year period from June 2017 to June 2018.

Methods: The study was performed with mandibular fractures in 60 volunteers. Into three categories, they were divided. These cases were examined in terms of postoperative complications at different intervals of postoperative visits and the variations between the three groups were evaluated. We also obtained and analyzed data on demographic characteristics, etiology, and fracture patterns of patients.

Results: Patients managed with a mini plate showed 20%, 30% and 50% less complications than the TOW group and MMF group, respectively. According to this study, mini plating was labeled as the most suitable method for the mandibular fractures treatment.

Conclusion: It was found that the rigid internal fixation in plates form has the advantage that it allows early or immediate mandibular mobility with good aesthetic and functional results and low complication rates.

Key words: Maxillomandibular fixation, mandibular fracture, mini - plating, transosseous wiring, postoperative complications.

Corresponding author:

Hafiz Hasan Fazal Sheikh,
Medical Officer, DHQ Hospital,
Hafizabad

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Since the mandible is the most commonly fractured bone the different methods suitable for the management of mandibular fractures are:

(a) Only Maxillomandibular fixation (MMF): for example. Braces, Arch bar.

(b) Maxillomandibular fixation by osteosynthesis, for example: peripheral wiring, external pin fixation and Transosseous wiring.

(c) Osteosynthesis without maxillomandibular fixation: p. for example. Compression and non-compression plates, Retaining screws, Mini plating.

Previously, conventional methods, ie, transosseous wiring and maxillomandibular fixation, were the most appropriate ways used to correct fractures of mandible and widely used methods still today. These procedures have different draw bags such as prevention of normal mandible function, limiting foods to liquid consistency, weight loss, oral hygiene problem and decreasing respiratory volume, a very distinct and sensitive bone in the face is mandible. The lower mandible fractures are twice common. Fractures result in severe function loss and deformity. The causes of the mandibular fracture are: interpersonal violence, traffic accidents, sports injuries, accidental falls, pathological fractures, industrial traumas, etc. In developing countries, interpersonal violence is related to alcohol. Any age group and sex may suffer from lower mandible trauma, but children under 12 are less susceptible to fracture because they are more resistant to bones. Proper management of the mandible fracture is necessary to correct congestion prior to injury to the patient and to prevent serious issues and 2ndry surgical intervention. The treatment of fractures of mandible varies according to presentation, surgical experience and available facilities in various maxillofacial units. The general principles of mandibular fractures are not different from the fractures treatment in other parts of the body. The fragments were positioned and then immobilized until bone fusion occurs, i.e., until reduction and fixation. To avoid or shorten the immobilization time

is applied for all these reasons, it is still for alternative treatment methods. There are several complications that may occur in jaw fracture after treatment, malocclusion, uncomplicated infection, poor union, nerve injury, Trismus, asymmetry and temporomandibular joint disorder.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In this clinical study, sixty patients underwent jaw fracture surgery in the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year period from June 2017 to June 2018. The subjects were divided into 3 groups and with 3 standard methods were treated. In each group 20 subjects were added.

(A) With transosseous wiring Maxillomandibular fixation (TOW)

(B) With dental wiring Maxillomandibular fixation (MMF)

(C) For short time maxillomandibular fixation done with Mini coating.

A quality examination of each patient was completed. Data on patient demography, etiology and fracture model were also obtained and analyzed. Orthopantomogram (OPG), if necessary, is standard radiography supported by a posterior view of the face or other face radiography.

For three months every case was followed.

Each patient monitoring was done with Postoperative orthopantomogram (OPG). During the follow-up period, any complications in the prophylaxis were recorded.

Data were analyzed with SPSS version 18.0. The significance test used was t-test and Chi-square test.

RESULTS:

75 patients of mandibular fractures were treated. Of these, 57 (92.93%) were male and the females were remaining 04 (6.7%) with male / female ratio was 15: 2. 27.2 years was the mean age of the selectees. The most frequent age group was 22-31 years, followed by 13-21 years. Figures 1 and 2.

Fig 1: Sex Distribution of patients

Fig 2: Age Distribution of Patients

Most of the patients were in the traffic accidents category upto (51%), less pathological and iatrogenic (1.7%). The results are shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3: Aetiology of injury

In our study, it was observed that mandibular fractures were more common in the parasphysis (48.3%) region, and 26.7% and 18.3% of the fractures were angular fractures. Details are given in figure 4.

Fig 4: Site of Fracture

60 cases were treated for mandibular fractures. Maxillomandibular fixation (MMF) was performed in the MMF group and the TOW group for a six-week period. In the plate group, only transient MMF was performed for 8-11 days.

TABLE 1: COMPLICATION RATES IN THE ENTIRE TREATMENT GROUP (n = 60)

Complications	No of patients	Percentage
Infection	6	10.0
Malocclusion	5	8.3
Malunion	3	5.0
Nonunion	0	0
Nerve Damage	3	5.0
TMJ-Dysfunction	3	5.0

Details of postoperative complications associated with various treatment modalities are given in Figure 5, Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 2: FREQUENCY OF COMPLICATIONS IN EACH CATEGORY

Complications	MMF	%	TOW	%	Plating	%
Infection	1	5.0	3	15.0	2	10.0
Malocclusion	1	5.0	2	10.0	2	10.0
Delayed union	2	10.0	1	5.0	0	0
Nonunion	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nerve Damage	0	0	3	15.0	0	0
TMJ-Dysfunction	2	10.0	1	5.0	0	0
OVERALL	6*	30.0	10*	50.0	4*	20.0

Twenty patients had twenty complications. 20% of these complications occurred in plaque group, 50% in TOW group and 30% in MMF group. Infection was the most common complication, occurring in 11% of patients and 2nd one was malocclusion in 8.4% of all cases.

DISCUSSION:

In this study, 50% of the fractures were due to traffic accident, 20% fall, 16.7% attack and 6.7% industrial fractures of trauma. Traffic accident findings are supported by Abbas and Moreno JC as the main reason of mandible, followed by a fall due to the flight of comets as Emshoff sports reported as the main cause of fractures of mandible. In our analysis, the kite-flying cause fractures of mandible in 21% of cases. The majority of patients were 93.3% of men, 6.7% of women and 14: 1 of men and women. 27 years was mean age of the patients. 2 years Age was between 13-61 of cases. 21 to 30 years was the most common age group followed by 12 to 60 years of age. Abbas et al and Mosby & Dugan reported a similar distribution by age and gender. Similarly, in males mandibular fractures were more common. The most common mandibular area in the fracture was paraphysis, representing 47.93% of the all. According to Renton and Moreno, in the jaw the paraphysis is the most common fracture site. The most common complication in this study was infection because it represented 11% of the all cases, followed by malocclusion in 8.3%. Different studies comparing traditional treatment methods with new techniques have been made. Compared Theriot, compression plates, TOW osteosynthesis and miniplate. Similarly, with TOW osteosynthesis Renton miniplates were compared. All of these have allowed a rigid internal fixation as the preferred treatment. Lamphier and Moulton discovered that conventional techniques were superior to new techniques for postoperative complications. In our study, the results show the differences between complications in each procedure. Considering that the number of complications in the samples (20 in each) and in each group (6, 10 and 4) was low, this difference was not statistically significant. However, the comparison is clinically important. In our study, infection occurred in 5% of the MMF group, 15% of the PULL group and 10% of the plaque group. Our postoperative infection results can be compared with international data. The MMF and coating rates were 4.4% and 12.5%, respectively, according to Moreno's infection. Similarly, Renton provided almost the same data for TOW (10%) and plates (15%). The highest infection rate for the TOW group and plates is likely to be paid to guide the intraoral contamination of the intraoral incision in the fracture

site. Other factors may be the type of fracture used, the type of treatment used, oral hygiene, the presence of broken teeth, a foreign body, mobility as the osteosynthesis material is the refractive zone etc. The patients were treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics. The second common problem was seen in the postoperative malocclusion group, 8.3% of the MMF group and 5% of the MMF group. Our data are compatible with Renton and Moreno et al. (MMF = 3.0% and 8.4% for other groups). In this study, Iizuka and Lindqvist reported no record of any involvement of the the facial nerve mandibular branch (motor disorder). Any reduction in opening of the mouth after surgery was accepted as trismus. In this study, trismus was found in three patients in one MMF group (11%) and one in TOW group (6%). Our findings on Trismus are comparable to those of Moreno. Our Anderson study also helps us discover that we do not have trismus in the plate group. The cause of postoperative trismus in the MMF group and in the TOW group is probably a longer period of maxillomandibular fixation (7 weeks). These patients were presented with their mouth open postoperative exercises (exercises with wooden sticks) and fortunately they were all released ten days a week.

CONCLUSION:

This analysis was carried out to know various modalities in the treatment of mandibular fractures. It has been observed that the rigid internal fixation in plates form has the advantage that it allows early or immediate mandibular mobility with better aesthetic and functional results and minimum complication rates. The infection was main operative morbidity, followed by malocclusion. Miniplate osteosynthesis decreased the complication rate compared to traditional methods.

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